

PROBLEMS WITH MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE FURNITURE MARKET.

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ABSTRACT

In this article, when buying furniture products, consumers use a wide range of information, namely: they analyze various information, try to find the best purchase option, choose a product in accordance with their lifestyle, taste and abilities. Financial, technical, time and psychological risks are also taken into account when a consumer purchases a durable product.

According to the study, when marketing furniture products, we had to study some of our national characteristics. That is, it turned out that the possibility and effectiveness of marketing significantly depends on the type of market, products produced and sold, and the scale of competition in the market. In particular, an important role is played by the lack of universal, standard, uniform recommendations in the application of the marketing concept; in practical marketing, everything differs significantly depending on external and internal factors, consumer characteristics.

In Uzbekistan 5-6 years ago the "gross" approach prevailed in the application of the marketing concept, but now a differentiated approach is widely

used. If we analyze the manufactured furniture products by content, 58% falls on household furniture, 39% - on corporate furniture and 3% - on other furniture. Office furniture and special furniture for educational institutions, retail stores, hospitals, restaurants, shops, warehouses, hairdressing salons constitute a significant share in this regard.

Analysis of the structure of furniture production by region showed that 52% of household furniture was sent to Tashkent, 14% - to Fergana region, 10% - to Tashkent region, 47% of office furniture - to Tashkent, 15% - to Samarkand region, 35% - to Tashkent. Kashkadarya region - 29%, Namangan region - 20%.

As mentioned above, the sustainable development of any industry is directly

related to the production and sale of goods that are only in demand. This, in turn, requires an effective organization of marketing activities of network enterprises, regular study of the furniture market, taking into account the wishes of consumers, a detailed analysis of the factors of the procurement process. Technological change, the growing role of social media, demographic changes and the increasing purchasing power of women are key aspects to consider in the marketing efforts of furniture manufacturers and retailers. We found it expedient to segment the furniture products of our country based on history, culture, customs, traditions and characteristics of furniture products while studying their desires.

When buying furniture products, consumers use a wide range of information, namely: they analyze various information, try to find the best purchase option, choose a product in accordance with their lifestyle, taste and abilities. The consumer also takes into account the financial, technical, temporary and psychological risks when purchasing durable goods.

Only after the buyer finds out the need to purchase household appliances, which consists of several interconnected stages, it will be possible to purchase and use it. That is, the general need is to solve the following tasks:

- determines which furniture will fully satisfy his needs;
- buys goods on the market, in a company store or on the Internet;
- What are the advantages of the product, what are the seller's guarantees, how long can this product be used?

To what extent do the media influence the purchase of furniture: analysis shows that 52.5% of the population buy TV along with household appliances, 43.1% from advertisements in newspapers and magazines, 49.7% from visits to brand stores, 50 , 6% - from catalogs. uses brochures.

Furniture manufacturers need to improve their positioning process in order to gain a competitive advantage and ensure that their products are stable in the target market and in the minds of consumers, which is clearly different from competitors' products. Enterprises in this area are making significant efforts to implement marketing activities to form a marketing mix. The result is lameness in the positioning process, which plays an important role in the systematic and effective marketing of enterprises.

Improper organization of the furniture manufacturers positioning process can lead to the following negative consequences:

- If the manufacturer does not determine the position of the product on the market, in this case the consumer can perform this task himself, and the company may not take the expected position and even lead to the formation of a negative image;
- The specificity of the product, which does not clearly indicate the features that distinguish it from competitors, or the creation of a position close to the position of competitors, may serve to negatively affect the consumer, and not induce him to buy the product;
- The lack of a clear position of the product can complicate the formation and

consistency of the marketing mix and even lead to a conflict of strategies for the formation of each element of the marketing mix.

- Even if the position is clearly chosen, but the limit is narrow, such a position can act as a force that prevents the company from expanding the market for existing products and introducing new products to the market. The main reason for this is the use of a unified brand strategy across the industry.

Based on the above, furniture manufacturers should focus on two main areas when implementing the positioning process:

- Determination of the point of correspondence or, in other words, the similarity of the positioned product. That is, on the basis of the study, it is necessary to determine in the minds of consumers which category of goods the enterprise identifies with the goods, or rather, to which category it belongs. This, in turn, makes it possible to identify its direct competitors based on the disclosure of the specifics of the product category.

- Determination of the point of differentiation of the positioned product. This includes demonstrating the competitive advantage of a product by identifying one or more distinguishing features that clearly distinguish it from the competition.

- Furniture manufacturers should consider the following industry specifics before positioning themselves in the above areas:

- The complexity of the production process and high technology efficiency. The production of modern furniture requires sophisticated technologies, which in turn leads to an increase in the market value of the brand.

- The duration of the start-up period for the production of furniture of a new type and model. The average time for launching the production of new model furniture by large furniture manufacturers is 7-15 months.

- High demand for product quality. Since furniture is a product that requires prior selection, consumers expect the product to have a long service life. Manufacturers in the industry use it to produce high quality fittings while maintaining their functional properties to maintain a high level of product quality. For this reason, many companies use the words "quality" and "reliability" to position their products.

Warranty service. Usually, the cost of warranty and post-warranty service is low, but in some cases it can reach 20-25 percent of the product cost. Also, the service of post-warranty collection of furniture can be up to 10% of the value of the goods.

The consumer spends a relatively large amount of time choosing and purchasing a product. Marketing research shows that in the consumer goods market, a consumer can spend up to 4 weeks choosing and purchasing furniture.

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